

BIG DATA MANAGEMENT AND CLOUD COMPUTING WITH POTENTIALITIES IN ACADEMIA: AN INDIAN SCENARIO

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Abstract

Development and progress are truly depends on knowledge dissemination and cultivation. Emerging technologies are the key pillar for complete industrial solutions and ultimately for the building of solid industrial society. And it is important step for reaching knowledge society development. Educational programs and courses play a greater role for such development. Social development is purely related economical progress and that is related with the educational delivery. In developing as well as under developed countries a true knowledge delivery system helps in promotion of all respects. Information Technologies is responsible for solid business solutions and improved business product thus depends on education. Several computing and information technology products were developed in our recent past. Cloud Computing, Green Computing, Data Science, Internet of Things (IoT), Business Analytics etc are important name in this regard. Countries like China, India, South Africa etc are doing well for solid infrastructure development. India is one of the largest educational hub in the world with about 40000+ HEIs (Higher Educational Institutes), but still there are lot of programs are missing in Indian academics. Though, India has huge potential to offer Bachelors, Masters and Doctoral Degrees in these areas with the use of proper and emerging educational policies and strategies. It is some extend true that India fails to offer such dynamic and up-to-date programs in some context. This paper is painted the running programs in India and also depicted possible nomenclature and program with industrial environment and context as per the international trends. Future potential of such program having SWOT are also depicted for making a true Digital India with smartest and effective way.

Keyword

Cloud Computing, Big Data Management, Green Computing, Virtualization, Analytics & Data Science, Higher Education, Training & Development, India, Knowledge Society, Digital India, Corporate Universities, Industrial Universities

Introduction

Data Science is governed by the Big Data Technologies and here importantly 'Big' is very large in nature and similarly Data is the raw information. In recent past technology had been changed and emerged continuously and here social media play an important role. The generation of data, information and similar content may be created few seconds from the users. Big-data or Big Data Management is dedicated for the data sets which are large enough. Sometime it is also responsible for the purely complex and traditional data processing. Big Data is similar to the Data Science as a field of study [1], [5], [14]. And it is also referred as Business Analytics as it is applicable in the business and corporate houses. Sometimes it is called as Analytics domain. Big Data and similar technologies is required for different kind of organizations (and sectors) which depends on Information or deals with information [4], [6], [15]. Hence it is applicable in diverse field and sectors viz. Healthcare, Banking and Finance, Information Foundations, Corporate sectors. The demands for the Big Data and Analytics, Data Science professionals have been emerged in the recent past in not only in developed but also in developing nations [2], [3], [8], [14]. Hence many universities around the world have started programs and educational opportunities in this field.

Objective

- To know about the basic of Higher Education systems in India.
- To learn about the basics of Big Data, Data Analytics and Data Sciences in detail.
- To know about the basics of Big Data Systems, Data Analytics and Cloud Computing including its allied branches in the academic space.
- To dig out the available program in the field of Computer Applications, Computer Science, Information Technology including emerging program in the areas viz. Cloud Computing and Data Sciences.
- To find out the latest and future/ possible areas and courses in the field of Cloud Computing, Data Sciences, Data Analytics etc in Indian context.

Methods

This is a conceptual paper and mainly deals with the overview of the emerging technologies within Information and Communication Technology Systems. Hence review of literature

methods play a good and vital role for doing this research work. Moreover the paper uses the URL of *MHRD (Govt. of India)* and *UGC (Govt. of India)* to learn about the education systems in India. Importantly to learn about the emerging and skill based program the URL also studied deeply. The Educational Research methodologies and Management research techniques have used to track the right picture.

Big Data and Cloud Computing: An Overview

Big Data Technologies is about the managing large number of data and complex data. Data Analytics is an important tool for the Data Analysis and Data representation. Big Data Management is helpful for the design and development of the storage systems and decision making as well. The large amount of Data Management as a field of study is called Data Science which comprises Data related areas, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence, Programming such as Python and/ Programming with 'R'. Cloud computing is software, applications and IT Infrastructure delivery in remote basis [7], [9], [10]. It is about the online availability of different infrastructure viz. hardware, software services and thus here serviceproviders offers variouskind of service. Here instead of physical infrastructure 'hardware-software' may be accessed with cloud based models [6], [11], [12].

Cloud Computing is lies on several virtualization principles and the foundations of the Cloud Computing are include cloud platform and cloud architecture. As far as **Public Cloud** is concerned an institution and organization may choose their services by the remote place as it is accessible by the internet. The features viz. elasticity, cost effective services etc play a great role in Cloud computing for the deployment of services. In this system need of deploying, managing, securing IT Systems is very much crucial for sustainable the infrastructure. **Private Cloud** basically host in-house services and infrastructure and it may be managed internally or externally by managing own infrastructure and normally hosted internally [8], [13], [16]. Combination of Private Cloud and Public Cloud Computing may be blended and it may be called as **Hybrid Cloud Computing**. A Hybrid Cloud Computing normally offers a large number of advantages than Public Cloud or Private Cloud in many various contexts [9], [16], [19].

Big Data as a Field of Study

Big Data and due to its importance in diverse field it has become an important subject now a days and universities internationally offers diverse range of programs in the fields in different levels viz. Bachelors Degree (mainly BS/BSc), Masters Degree (mainly MS/MSc) with different nomenclature such as Big Data Management, Business Analytics, Data Science etc. Though a very few universities also offered program with the tag MPhil and PhD. The table 1 shows the list of few universities that are offers Masters program in the field and a majority of them are from United Kingdom. The same program is also offered in different faculties in different universities viz. Faculty of Computing/IT, Faculty of Business/ Management and so on.

Table: 1-Some of the International Universities offering Data Science and allied programs

Universities	Offered Degrees
Sheffield University, UK	MSc-Data Science
City University, London, UK	MSc-Data Science
Goldsmith University of London, UK	MSc-Data Science
Lancaster University, UK	MSc-Data Science
University of Glasgow, UK	MSc-Data Science
Kings College, London, UK	MSc-Data Science
University of Southampton, UK	MSc-Data Science
Brunel University, London, UK	MSc-Data Science & Analytics
Swansea University, UK	MSc-Health Data Science
University of Stirling, Scotland	MSc- Big Data
University of Dundee, UK	MSc-Data Engineering
Asia Pacific University of Technology & Innovation, Malaysia	MSc-Data Science & Business Analytics
National University of Singapore, Singapore	MSc- Business Analytics

Cloud Computing as a Field of Study

Due to the importance of Cloud Computing and allied technologies it has today applicable in different organizations and institutions and even it is responsible for the creation of Digital Life and Society [12], [17], [20]. Hence for the wider uses and importance of the technology in

different areas and space it has now become a Science and full-fledged subjects in many universities [13], [18], [21]. Many international universities have started program in different levels viz.

- Masters Degree
- Bachelors Degree
- Post Graduate Diploma
- Post Graduate Certificate
- Diploma
- Certificate etc

The Program in some cases is available as a Full Fledged Degree and in other cases as a Major, Specialization or Honors. Among the few reputed international universities few important are listed in Table: 2.

Table: 2-Some of the International Universities offering Cloud Computing and allied programs

Programs	University
MSc-Cloud Computing	University of Newcastle
MSc-Cloud Computing	Cork Institute of Technology
MSc-Cloud Computing	University of Essex
MSc-Cloud Computing	University of Leicester
MSc-Cloud Computing	Anglia Ruskin University
MSc-Computing (Cloud Computing)	Dublin City University
MSc-Cloud & Enterprise Computing	Nottingham Trent University
MSc-Advance Computer Science (Cloud Computing)	University of Leeds
MSc- Network Management & Cloud Computing	Middlesex University, Dubai

Though, as far as India is concerned very few educational institutes have started the program with Full Fledged Degree/ Major/ Specialization/ Honors. And among these most are belongs from either Private Universities, Deemed Universities and exceptionally State and Central Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore

University could be able to find out. The table: 3 is showing a list of universities offering the advanced and higher Degree (i.e. MTech) in Cloud Computing and Allied areas.

Table: 3-Some of the Indian Universities offers MTech in Cloud Computing and allied areas

Universities	States	Type of University	Programs
VIT University	Tamilnadu	Private-Deemed	MTech-CSE (Cloud Computing).
Amity University	Uttarpradesh	Private-State	MTech-Cloud Computing.
Vel Tech University	Tamilnadu	Private-Deemed	MTech (IT Infrastructure and Cloud Computing).
SRM University	Tamilnadu	Private-Deemed	MTech- Cloud Computing.
KL University	Andhrapradesh	Private-Deemed	MTech- Cloud Computing.

Even few universities have also started higher degrees leading to MPhil and PhD in the areas of Cloud Computing and Allied Sciences. Among these important is MPhil in Data Analytics & Cloud Computing/ MPhil in Big Data and Business Analytics. MPhil in Business Analytics and Cloud Computing offered by the Srinivas University, Karnataka.

India, Higher Education and Big Data and Cloud Computing Management

India is growing and developing rapidly and it has large number of Higher Educational Institutes (40000+) and among these 800+ are degree awarding bodies viz.

- Central Universities
- State Universities
- Private Universities
- Deemed Universities even
- Institutes of National Importance (INIs)

And importantly apart from these there are many (about 5000) Engineering and Technological Colleges and institutions but practically it is very difficult to find out the institutes offering the programs in the field including Cloud Computing, Big Data and allied areas. Initially if starting a full fledged program is difficult or not suitable then the program may be started as a specializations. Moreover here program are proposed of another nomenclature called MSc-Engg. The details are proposed and provided in table: 4.

Table: 4-Some of the possible programs in Engineering track in Indian context

Engineering/Technology: Cloud Computing	
BTech/BE/ BSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)- Cloud Computing (CC)	MTech/ME/MSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)-Cloud Computing
BTech/BE/ BSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)- Cloud Computing & Virtualization	MTech/ME/ MSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)--Cloud Computing & Virtualization
BTech/BE/BSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)- Cloud & Green Computing	MTech/ME / MSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)-Cloud & Green Computing
BTech/BE/ BSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)- Cloud & Enterprise Computing	MTech/ME / MSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)-Cloud & Enterprise Computing
BTech/BE/ BSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)- Cloud Computing & Informatics	MTech/ME / MSc-Engg. (CSE/IT)-Cloud Computing & Informatics

Though as far as India is concerned several concern are important and valuable in different context which include but not limited to the—

- Cloud Computing as well Data Science are valuable domain in today’s context not only in industries but also in academia and research.
- Cloud Computing is useful in different industries, organizations, institutions regardless of Government or Private, Profit Making or Non Profit based for enhancing IT infrastructure and systems.
- Cloud Computing and Big Data is rapidly gaining as a Diploma, Degree and PG Degree in the field of *Computing, IT, IT Management* curriculum as a paper/course/ gradients.
- Initially Cloud Computing and allied Programs internationally started in the European Countries mainly in the United Kingdom.
- Cloud Computing is mainly offered as BSc/ MSc in international universities, though as far as India is concerned though limited number of universities have started program with BTech/MTech
- In some cases the Cloud Computing program is also related and available with Big Data Management, Data Analytics or simply ‘Analytics’ etc.

Concluding Remarks

Developing countries today purely depends on information transparencies and information knowledge cycles. And importantly here some of the emerging programs viz. Cloud

Computing & Analytics are helpful in many ways. Universities need proper planning, initiation and implementation for starting emerging programs like Cloud Computing, Data Science etc. not only in their curriculum but also full-fledged degree/ Minor/Major in other allied branches viz. Computing, IT, Information Sciences, Management Science, Mathematical Science etc. But for all these dealing following are crucial and important.

- Proper collaboration as well as tie-up is also required for solid implementation of the Cloud and Data Science in the academia in a country like India.
- Different type of Organizations/ Institutions and among the Universities need a proper communication in-between for real life development of the projects and complete manpower development.
- It is essential to start Corporate Universities as well as collaborative research centers keeping in view the need of subjects, domains etc for the development.

In a developing countries like India, Pakistan, Indonesia, Brazil, South Africa etc initially it may be difficult to start Cloud and Big Data and other allied program for healthy and developed Information Infrastructure System building and Management.

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